

LAKBAY-DIWA ✨
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

JANUARY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES

of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

ARNOLD P. CANDAY, EdD

Assistant Professor IV

JH Cerilles State College

Zamboanga del Sur, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18309146](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18309146)

CHEERS SA USA!

Cheers sa usa nga naghatag ug time,
Bisan walay balos, still stood in line.
Nga nangayo ug pasaylo, with voice so true,
Ug gipasaylo usab, with a promise to renew.

Cheers sa usa nga gibiyaan sa dalan,
Yet carried the pain, but moved on tanan.
Nga gihandom gihapon ang sweet memories,
Even when silence replaced old melodies.

Cheers sa usa nga nagtuo gihapon,
Though trials came, faith was never gone.
Nga mipadayon sa damgo, bisan walay kauban,
Still chasing dreams, bisan walay kasaligan.

Cheers sa usa nga milahutay sa kasakit,
Who fought through struggles, though body felt weak.
Nga nagpadayon sa kinabuhi nga lisod,
Spirit stayed strong, hope never eroded.

Cheers to you, sa imong kusog ug gugma,
You are the light in darkest drama.
Ikaw ang pahiyom sa kasakit nga gibati,
Ikaw ang kahayag sa akong kinabuhi.